

Project Brand Book

Introduction

The purpose of this brand book is to assist the Consortium in using the EXCALIBUR logo appropriately.

It is also a useful aid when instructing typographers and others assigned with the production of branded items to design and create EXCALIBUR communication materials in an adequate manner.

In order to maintain the integrity of the visual identity of the project it is important to apply all the elements of the present guide properly and consistently.

EXCALIBUR
Preserving the Past, Unveiling the Future.

Funded by
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Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
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Primary version

The *EXCALIBUR* logo consists of a **symbol**, the **project title** and a **tagline**. It represents symbolic elements related to digitalization and cultural heritage.

The symbol, paired with a bright terracotta and bright teal colour scheme, integrates geometric shapes, stylized archaeological motifs, and a dotted digital structure, to convey a fusion of ancient heritage and advanced technology.

Important note: In line with the [ECCCH Guidelines](#), the *ECHOES* logo is used in its symbol form, adapted to the logo colours of *EXCALIBUR* both in its horizontal and vertical versions. The *ECHOES* symbol form appears first, followed by a separated line, and then the logo

Vertical options

In addition to the primary version in horizontal plane, the logo is available in two vertical options to afford tailored display in all available layouts.

The vertical options are compliant with the afore-mentioned ECCCH Guidelines as well.

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Negative version

In cases of dark, coloured and/or patterned backgrounds, the negative version of the project logo should be used to maintain contrast levels, thus ensuring proper visibility

Instructions | Placing

Clear space surrounding the project logo should remain free of competing texts, logos, images or any other visual element that could interfere with the logo. The indicative space should be set at approximately 1/3 of the logo dimensions.

Instructions | Display

The logo should be used mainly on a white (i.e., bright and simple) background in its primary version for maximum impact and clarity. The display should comply with the versions that are specified in this guide.

The logo may not appear in any other colours and versions than the predefined. The logo should not be altered in any shape or format or even combined with any other element such as other logos, words, graphics, photos, slogans or symbols.

Colour Scheme

The Excalibur colour scheme consists of the following:

Dark Blue	HEX: #182D4B RGB: 24, 45, 75 CMYK: 99, 81, 41, 42
Bright Terracotta	HEX: #E35336 RGB: 227, 83, 54 CMYK: 4, 79, 80, 0
Bright Teal	HEX: #00D0DC RGB: 0, 208, 220 CMYK: 66, 0, 20, 0
Light Grey	HEX: #D1D5DB RGB: 209, 213, 219 CMYK: 21, 13, 12, 0
Text Colour	HEX: #00000 RGB: 0, 0, 0 CMYK: 91, 79, 62, 97

Important note: RGB colour codes are used on web applications, the CMYK colour codes are used in printing materials

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Font Family

The project uses a specific font and its complementary formats

- ✓ Open Sans (for Headings, Titles and normal text, subtitles and captions)

This font must be opted for all communication materials, online and print, as well as in web and media applications wherever this is possible (i.e. at the project website), to retain consistency. Replacing the given font should be avoided.

Open Sans (Regular)
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890!@#&%*

Open Sans (Bold)
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890!@#&%*

Open Sans (Italic)
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
*1234567890!@#&%**

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Text formats and configurations

Text Format	Configurations				
	Font	Size	Style	Colour	Alignment
Heading 1	Open Sans	24	Normal	# E35336	Justified
Heading 2	Open Sans	18	Normal	#182D4B	Justified
Heading 3	Open Sans	14	Normal	#182D4B	Justified
Heading 4	Open Sans	12	Normal	#182D4B	Justified
Normal Text	Open Sans	12	Normal	#000000	Justified
Captions	Open Sans	11	Italics	#182D4B	Centered

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